

BROMINATION OF COUMARINS. PART II. BROMINATION OF
6-HYDROXY-4-METHYLCOUMARIN AND ITS METHYL ETHER

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6-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and its methyl ether have been brominated and mono, di- and tribromo derivatives obtained.

In continuation of the work described in part I (*this Journal*, 1949, 26, 359) the bromination of 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and its methyl ether has been studied.

Borsche (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2732) carried out the bromination of 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with two molecules of bromine and arbitrarily assigned the constitution of 6-hydroxy-5:7-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin to the product obtained. In the bromination of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (part I) it has been found that the first bromine atom enters the 3-position and the subsequent bromine atoms enter the benzene ring. It was therefore of interest to study the bromination of 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and its methyl ether systematically.

6-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (I, R=H) on bromination with one molecule of bromine did not give a pure product. Its methyl ether (I, R=Me), however, under the same conditions of bromination gave a bromo compound to which the structure of 6-methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (II, R=Me; R'=R''=H) was assigned, as it gave a coumarilic acid derivative (III, R=Me; R'=R''=H) on treatment with alkali. This methoxy bromocoumarin on demethylation with anhydrous aluminium chloride gave 6-hydroxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (II, R=R'=R''=H).

6-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin on bromination with two molecules of bromine in acetic acid at the temperature of the water-bath gave a dibromo compound (A, m.p. 276-80°). However, when the bromination was carried out in acetic acid solution with two molecules of bromine in presence of sodium acetate, as done by Borsche (*loc. cit.*), another dibromo compound (B, m.p. 201-203°), probably identical with Borsche's derivative (m.p. 202-203°), was obtained. Borsche has arbitrarily assigned to it the structure of 6-hydroxy-5:7-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin. Both the compounds (A) and (B) were methylated. Both the dibromocoumarins on hydrolysis gave coumarilic acid derivatives, thus indicating that one of the bromine atoms in both was in 3-position. The other

bromine atom must therefore be either in the 5- or in the 7-position. The structure assigned by Borsche to the dibromocoumarin is therefore incorrect. The structures of 6-hydroxy-3:7-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (II, $R=R'=H$; $R''=Br$) and 6-hydroxy-3:5-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (II, $R=R''=H$; $R'=Br$) are provisionally assigned on stereochemical grounds to (A) and (B) respectively.

If we assume that in the coumarin ring system the double bond is fixed between the benzene ring and the α -pyrone ring (cf. Mills and Nixon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2510; Rangaswami and Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 14A, 547; Thakor and Shah, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1947, XVI, Part 3, p. 38) the 5-position ought to be more reactive than the 7-position, because there is a double bond between the fifth and the sixth carbon atoms and the sixth carbon atom carries the hydroxyl group (Formula IV). However, owing to the steric hindrance of the hydroxyl group in 6-position and the methyl group in 4-position, the bromine atom is not likely to enter the 5-position with ease. In the case of the bromination of 6-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin the steric hindrance will be more marked due to the methoxy group and therefore it is presumed that the only dibromo product obtained on bromination may be 6-methoxy-3:7-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (II, $R=Me$; $R'=H$, $R''=Br$). This compound is identical with the methyl ether of (A); therefore A is probably 6-hydroxy-3:7-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin. It follows therefore that (B) must be 6-hydroxy-3:5-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin.

Both (A) and (B) on further bromination gave the same 3:5:7-tribromo derivative (II, $R=H$, $R'=R''=Br$) which was also obtained on bromination of 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with excess of bromine. Attempts to prepare the tribromo derivative of 6-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin did not succeed, only the dibromo compound was obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin was prepared according to Borsche (*loc. cit.*) and methylated with dimethyl sulphate and alkali (Desai and Mavani, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 15A, 11).

6-Methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin.—The coumarin (I, $R=Me$; 1.9 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (10 c.c.) by heating, and bromine (1.6 g., 1 mol.) in acetic acid (16 c.c.) added to the hot solution. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 4 hours and then diluted with water. The separated solid was crystallised from dilute alcohol in faint yellow glistening needles, m.p. 125-27°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: Br, 29.9. $C_{11}H_9O_3Br$ requires Br, 29.7 per cent).

6-Hydroxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin.—6-Methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) was intimately mixed with powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (4 g) and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 150°-160° for 3 hours. It was then cooled and treated with ice and concentrated hydrochloric acid and the solid obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 258-60°, yield 0.6 g. (Found: Br, 31.2. $C_{10}H_7O_3Br$ requires Br, 31.4 per cent). It forms orange-yellow alkali salts which are sparingly soluble in water.

5-Methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic Acid.—The bromocoumarin (II, R=Me, R'=R''=H) (1 g.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide solution (1 N, 20 c.c.) for 3 hours. It was acidified and the precipitated solid was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in small white plates, m.p. 208° (decomp.), yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 63.8; H, 4.7. C₁₁H₁₀O₄ requires C, 64.1; H, 4.8 per cent). It gives a violet coloration on warming with concentrated sulphuric acid.

6-Hydroxy-3: 7 (or 5)-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (A).—The coumarin (I, R=H) (1.76 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (15 c.c.) by heating and bromine (3.2 g., 2 mols.) in acetic acid (32 c.c.) added. The reaction mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for 2 hours. The product which separated out was crystallised from acetic acid in small yellow plates, m. p. 276-80°, yield 1.2 g. (Found: Br, 47.6. C₁₀H₈O₃ Br₂ requires Br, 47.9 per cent).

The *methyl ether* of the above bromocoumarin was prepared by refluxing it with methyl iodide in acetone solution in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate, m. p. 205-207°. (Found: Br, 45.9. C₁₁H₈O₃Br₂ requires Br, 46.0 per cent). This was found to be identical with 6-methoxy-3: 7 (or 5)-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (described below) prepared by the direct bromination of 6-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin.

6-Hydroxy-3: 5 (or 7)-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (B).—The coumarin (I, R=H) (1.76 g) and crystalline sodium acetate (3.5 g.) were dissolved in acetic acid (30 c.c.) by heating and bromine (3.2 g., 2 mols.) in acetic acid (32 c.c.) added gradually with shaking to the hot solution. The product which separated out on cooling was crystallised from dilute alcohol in silky white needles, m. p. 201-203°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: Br, 47.8. C₁₀H₈O₃Br₂ requires Br, 47.9 per cent). It forms orange-yellow alkali salts which are sparingly soluble in water.

The *methyl ether* of the above bromocoumarin was prepared by refluxing a solution of the bromocoumarin in acetone with methyl iodide and anhydrous potassium carbonate for 20 hours, m. p. 212-14°. (Found: Br, 45.6. C₁₁H₈O₃Br₂ requires Br, 46.0 per cent).

6-Methoxy-3: 7 (or 5)-dibromo-4 methylcoumarin.—The coumarin (I, R=Me; 2 g.) was treated with liquid bromine (5 c.c., excess) and the mixture was allowed to stand for 48 hours. The residual solid was treated with sodium bisulphite solution to remove the excess of bromine. The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in silky white needles, m. p. 205-207°, yield 2.5 g. Mixed melting point with the methyl ether of the dibromocoumarin (A) was not lowered. Mixed melting point with the methyl ether of the dibromocoumarin (B) was lowered to 182°. The same dibromo product was obtained when the bromination was carried out with excess of bromine in presence of sodium acetate.

5-Methoxy-6 (or 4)-bromo-3-methylcoumarilic Acid.—6-Methoxy-3: 7 or 5-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide solution (1 N, 20 c. c.) for 3 hours. The solid separating on acidification was crystallised from acetic acid in white needles; m. p. 274-76° (decomp.), yield 0.6 g (Found: Br, 28.2. C₁₁H₉O₄Br requires Br, 28.1 per cent). It gives a violet coloration when warmed with concentrated sulphuric acid.

5-Hydroxy-4 (or 6)-bromo-3-methylcoumarilic Acid.—The dibromocoumarin (B, 1 g.) was refluxed with sodium-carbonate solution (5%, 20 c.c.) for 3 hours. The solid obtained on acidification was crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) in brownish yellow shining needles, m. p. 238-40° (decomp.) (Found: Br, 29.5. $C_{10}H_7O_4Br$ requires Br, 29.5 per cent).

6-Hydroxy-3,5:7-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin.—The coumarin (I, R=H) (2 g.) was treated with liquid bromine (5 c.c., excess) and the reaction mixture was kept for 48 hours. The residual solid was treated with sodium bisulphite solution to remove the excess of bromine and crystallised from acetic acid in short colorless needles, m. p. 196-98°, yield 2.8 g. (Found: Br, 58.1. $C_{10}H_5O_4Br_3$ requires Br, 58.1 per cent). It forms orange-yellow alkali salts which are sparingly soluble in water.

The *methyl ether* of the above compound was prepared by refluxing it with methyl iodide in acetone solution in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. It was crystallised from acetic acid in small, yellow needles, m. p. 174-76°. (Found: Br, 56.5. $C_{11}H_7O_3Br_3$ requires Br, 56.2 per cent).

5-Hydroxy-4:6-dibromo-3-methylcoumarilic Acid.—The bromocoumarin (II, R=H; R'=R''=Br) (1 g.) was refluxed with sodium carbonate solution (5%, 20 c.c.) for 3 hours. The solid separating on acidification was crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) in small brownish plates, m. p. 180° (decomp.), yield 0.4 g. (Found: Br, 45.4. $C_{10}H_5O_4Br_2$ requires Br, 45.7 per cent).

Thanks of the authors are due to Dr. R. C. Shah for his kind interest in the work.

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Received June 14, 1949